

NESTORE

D5.4 Social Platform

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Short Abstract

This document presents the deliverable D5.4 (Social Platform – Demonstrator) of WP5 (NESTORE Virtual Coach) and contains the main results of discussions and activities performed during Task 5.4 (Social platform).

In this document, we briefly remind the goals of the NESTORE social platform and how it interconnects to the other components of WP5 and the other WPs (Section 1). The main part of the document (Section 2) provides an overview of the different functionalities that we developed in this demonstrator.

Finally, the last section provides the references, the links and the credentials necessary to explore and test the NESTORE Social Platform.

Key Words

Social platform, social media, e-coaching, health, older adults, companion, demonstrator.

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1 Introduction

The following excerpts from the grant agreement describe the vision for the NESTORE social platform.

The importance of the social platform emerges in the description of WP5. “The main objective of WP5 is to design the interaction with and to develop the interface for a personalized coach and the ecosystem of NESTORE resources (such as games, social platforms, smartphone apps, tangible and vocal interfaces) that support user’s self-reflection and training in the 5 dimensions of wellbeing.

The coaching on the different pathways will be supported through different techniques: “[...] 3) social and environmental support through the social platform.”

“The main goal of the social platform is the possibility to share and offer knowledge and services provided by the users to other users. These knowledge and services will be targeted at supporting the achievement of personal goals in the different dimensions of the interventions. In particular, users with a high intrinsic capacity in one dimension (e.g., cooking skills or mobility skills) can support other users in the achievement of their goal in the respective dimension, increasing the functional abilities of the beneficiary of this knowledge or of these services. This participatory valorisation of individual user skills will empower older adults, rewarding their individual abilities towards a perspective of successful ageing, which in the end facilitates continuous engagement in the platform.”

As stated above, the social platform will not be a separate component of NESTORE but it will be a part of the coaching ecosystem and therefore, the NESTORE app “will also allow the access to the social platform”. This close integration is also visible in the conception of the mobile app with which the Social platform shares a common calendar to schedule and get reminders about activities.

Finally, the social platform will also provide information to the virtual coach that, through the Decision Support System will access to the user’s network “allowing to better exploit the personal network of contacts and the nearby service providers (e.g., healthcare systems, shops, gyms) for increasing the user’s functional capacity in the chosen intervention dimension.”

1.1 Interlinks with other Work Packages

The Social platform belongs to WP 5, as task 5.4. The role of the Social platform is related to many other components of the NESTORE ecosystem. In the following paragraphs, we shortly describe its connections with the other WPs and specifically with the various products of NESTORE.

WP3 – NESTORE Monitoring System

- Within the Monitoring System, the social platform allows the user to check his/her physiological data and setup sensors such as the NESTORE’s bracelet and the smart scale.

WP4 – NESTORE Decision Support System:

The Decision Support System suggests coaching activities through the app or the tangible coach. For the social domain, these activities are suggested through the social platform. An example can be an event added by the user in the social platform’s calendar. WP5 – NESTORE Virtual Coach:

- The Social platform is part of the NESTORE Virtual Coach and, alongside the mobile app, the tangible coach and the serious game, it is one of its main ways for the system to set and check user preferences and to provide tailored advices. The Social platform is especially connected with the mobile app through a synchronized calendar of the coaching activities.

WP6 – Integration of the NESTORE System:

- The calendar displayed in the Social platform is central to coordinate the daily and weekly activities of the users. This calendar is constantly synchronized with the personal calendar in the mobile app and it allows to check availabilities also of different users and friends.

WP7 – User Perspectives: from Co-Design to Piloting:

- The deliverable D7.1 reported the first phase of research about the co-design in NESTORE and details the method applying in this study. The main outcome related to social domain is the vision that participants had about the social dimension within activities. Independently from the domain of the activity (physical, cognitive, etc.), the social dimension is seen by most of the participants as a strong motivating factor for engagement. In particular, socialising and engaging in activities with other people was a significant theme that ran throughout all workshops. Participants spoke of the importance and value of interacting with family, of engaging in intergenerational activity and being with others. In terms of motivation, participants spoke of the importance of the social element of activities as a motivating factor, particularly if these latter ones could be undertaken with friends and family. While social connections are perceived as important, the same is not true when these connections are too much technologically led, thus pulling people away from “real life” connections.
- During subsequent workshops held in Barcelona and Vlaardingen (July 2018), the participants confirmed the vision of the social platform as a facilitator: first, to virtually connect people on the same area with similar interests; second, to help bringing these exchanges in real-life. The participants find interesting the idea of having activities available in the neighbourhood suggested by the coach.
- In summary, from both the literature review and the workshops’ analysis, it emerges that the social platform acts as a facilitator, connecting on the one hand side users with similar interests and living in the same area, and motivating users to exchange in real-life.

2 Demonstrator

2.1 Description of the demonstrator

The social platform is composed of six pages: Home, Places, Forum, Blog, How to and Dashboard. While the first five sections are accessible (with limited rights) to anyone, the Dashboard is available only for logged-in NESTORE's users. A menu in the top of the page allows to navigate through the different functionalities.

In order to adapt to the need of NESTORE's users, the platform has been conceived and developed using an iterative approach based on the output of workshops of WP7 (see previous section). To be more suitable for an everyday use also on mobile, the system was developed using responsive web design.

The whole platform supports multi-language (currently the project's languages are: English, Italian, Spanish, and Dutch).

The next sections will describe one after another the structure, the characteristics and the goals of the different pages.

2.1.1 Home

The goal of the homepage is to present a quick and easy overview of all the services available on the platform and an update of the last content and activities added on the platform by other users. From the top to the bottom, this page shows an overview about the last blog articles added into the platform, a selection of the events that the user may want to join and the recent activity in the forum (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Home page. In the top menu, you can notice the “Dashboard” item is visible and accessible as the NESTORE's user is logged in.

2.1.2 Places

The goal of this page is to provide full access to the “Places” presents on the platform. A “Place” is a geo-localised activity or event with a start and end date that a user may choose to join. “Places” are categorized according to four of the five NESTORE domains: Social, Physical, Cognitive and Nutritional domains. A “Place” may have multiple tags for activities that concern multiple domains (e.g., running with friends will be related to the social and physical domains).

The top of the page presents a map view of the places allowing the user to browse the nearest activities directly from the chart (see Figure 2). The same page presents also the activities in the form of a list with additional information such as a picture, the average users’ rating, a short description and the time of the activity. The user can directly select one of the proposed activities, get a long description (see below the map), and perform a research using the search field and/or the filters. In this case, the results are presented in a specialized page that facilitate the navigation of events (e.g., a mini-map follows the user while scrolling the events, with an animated pin highlighting the location of the event).

Figure 2. Places - Main page.

By selecting a specific “Place”, the user obtains a more in-depth description of the event such as photos, comments, related Places, etc. (see Figure 3). Users have the possibility to add their own comments and to share the Place by e-mail or using other social networks (e.g., Facebook, LinkedIn, WhatsApp). Finally, if they want to join the event, they can simply add it to their NESTORE’s calendar. Through the Decision

Support System, the Virtual coach will consider this new entry and, at the due time, it will send a reminder, ask for feedback and consider the accomplished activity in the context of the user's pathway.

Finally, this page provides access to external links to events promoted by related local associations. These links as well as all the propositions added to Places need to be approved by the NESTORE admin or moderators. The review process is communicated to the users by e-mail, step by step, from the submission of a proposition to the acceptance/refusal.

The screenshot shows the NESTORE Places website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for HOME, FORUM, and BLOG. Below this is the NESTORE Places logo and a search bar. The main content area features a large image of a Warhol portrait. To the right of the image is a calendar widget titled 'Add to My Calendar' for August 2019, with a duration selector (1, 2, 3, or 4 hours) and an 'Add' button. Below the image, there is a section for 'Place Category: Social' and 'Place Tags: monza'. The main text describes the event: 'Andy Warhol a Monza è già un successo: 3200 visitatori in soli 15 giorni di apertura. Biglietti d'ingresso ridotti per i visitatori della Reggia di Monza.' It also mentions that 3200 visitors attended in the first 15 days and that the exhibition is open until April 28, 2019.

Figure 3. Places - Activity description. The central part shows the description and the other details of the activity. On the right side, the interface offers the possibility to easily add the event to the user's calendar for a given duration.

2.1.3 Dashboard

The Dashboard is the more "technical" page of the platform; it gives a quick access to the content reserved to the NESTORE's users.

First of all, the Dashboard provides an overview of the user's activity on the platform (see Figure 4). For instance, it shows the stats about the use of the forum and the blog, and it provides generic information about the user's network (e.g., number of connected friends) and it works as a reminder for the users that did not complete yet their profile.

Figure 4. Dashboard - Main page.

In addition to these functionalities, the Dashboard allows a direct access to many other services and parameters, such as:

- The user profile;
- The user's calendar;
- The preferences related to the different domains (see Figure 5);
- The information stored by the sensors (i.e., the smart scale and the wearable);
- Additional information such as Privacy Policy and Terms of use.

Finally, the Dashboard is also the place where users can manage their network. Here, they can invite friends to join NESTORE or follow other NESTORE's users to get notification about their activity on the platform (e.g., a new post in the blog).

Figure 5. Dashboard - Preferences.

2.1.4 Forum and Blog

The Forum and the Blog present the standard functionalities that a user may expect from these tools.

The Forum is conceived as a virtual place to meet and discuss (Figure 6). It is initiated by the NESTORE's Admins (i.e., superusers with special privileges needed to administer and maintain the system) who propose topics that may interest the NESTORE's users. However, any user can propose a new theme or discussion that will be moderated by the NESTORE Admins and added in the forum after approval. According to our vision, this is the place in which users with a high intrinsic capacity in one dimension (e.g., cooking skills) can support other users in the achievement of their goals through mutual care. This would ideally also support the self-esteem of those skilled users who would be given the possibility to share their skills with others and thus act as co-mentors or additional coaches.

Category	Subcategories	Topics	Posts	
Community Subcategories: Diaries, Games, Humor, Introductions, Support & Suggestion	5	7	23	Leave
Join Entertainment and hobbies Subcategories: Computers & Phones, Hobbies & Crafts, Home, Movies, Outdoors, More »	10	22	74	
Join Off Topic	0	1	2	
Join Retirement Subcategories: Financial, Health Insurance, Retirement Living, Seniors Living Alone	4	10	24	
Join Senior Discussions Subcategories: Family & Relationships, Health & Wellness, Holidays and Traditions	3	8	24	

Figure 6. Forum.

The goals of the Blog is to present articles on specific topics related to the NESTORE’s domains or to subjects that may interest the users (Figure 7). Only NESTORE’s users can publish an article; when they publish it, they can choose to make it available to everyone or only to other NESTORE’s users. In this last case, the people in the user’s network will get a notification through their wall accessible via the Dashboard.

The screenshot shows the NESTORE Blog interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for HOME, DASHBOARD, FORUM, BLOG, HOW TO, and PLACES. The user's name, Francesco Carrino, is displayed in the top right corner. Below the navigation bar, the page title is "Nestore > Blog". A search bar is located at the top left of the main content area. The main content area displays a list of blog posts. The first post is titled "What are the best vitamins for dementia patients? 11 vitamins, minerals and herbs to improve well-being" and is dated 11/9/18. It includes a small image of various fruits and vegetables. The second post is titled "10 tips for elders to meet their nutrition goals" and is also dated 11/9/18. It includes a small image of a bowl of soup. The third post is titled "What are instrumental activities of daily living?" and is dated 11/9/18. It includes a small image of an elderly person. On the right side of the page, there is a sidebar with a search bar and a list of related articles, including "What are the best vitamins for dementia patients?", "How poor vision and peripheral vascular disease affect balance", "Managing multiple health conditions: what care recipients and caregivers want each other to know", "What are instrumental activities of daily living?", and "10 tips for elders to meet their nutrition goals". At the bottom right of the page, there are links for "Settings" and "Online Friends (0)".

Figure 7. Blog.

2.1.5 How to

“How to” contains special articles describing different parts of the NESTORE ecosystem and, if needed, how to set them up (Figure 8). These articles usually have the form of an online presentation (see Figure 9). As any online course, users can navigate the content following their own rhythm.

Figure 8. "How to" page.

Figure 9. "How to" page – slide from the tutorial "How to join Nestore platform".

2.2 Link(s)

Web platform: <https://my.nestore-coach.eu/>

Credentials to log in and test the platform will be provide upon request.

